

Miller

Dearraindrop

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Biographical information

Dearraindrop is a five-member art collective based out of Virginia Beach, VA. The aim of our work is to create environments that submerge the participant in a sea of inter-related sound and visual elements. Our shows utilize painting, interactive sculpture, musical instruments, collage, video, clothing, and drawing to create a vibrant, immersive atmosphere. We have had solo shows in Tokyo, Oslo, Stockholm, Toronto, Copenhagen, Padova, and New York. We often perform at our shows with acoustic and electronic musical instruments we have created, reinforcing the link between the visual and auditory worlds.

Description of Piece

The installation includes several of our most recent musical instruments and sculptures displayed on a section of wall. These instruments range from completely autonomous (as in the Color Wheels) to fully human-controlled (as in the Video Piano). A background layer of sound emerges from the autonomous instruments, and participants are invited to add to it by playing the interactive ones.

